

White Paper ID Number	W040
Title of White Paper	Theoretical Astrophysics in Canada
ID of Associated Expression of Interest	E070
Topic Area of White Paper	other (specify in comments below)

Executive Summary of White Paper (5000 character limit)

Theory plays an essential role in astrophysics, both in planning and motivating observations or experiments, and in extracting deeper understanding from their findings. As investment in infrastructure grows, co-investment in theory should follow. Canada has established a particularly strong reputation in theoretical astrophysics, with leadership in many fields, and institutions and programs of international stature. We propose strategic ways to build on these strengths so that the investments across astronomy recommended in the LRP reach their full potential.

Lead author and affiliation James E. Taylor, University of Waterloo

Email address of lead author taylor@uwaterloo.ca

Other authors and affiliations

J. Richard Bond (CITA), Jo Bovy (Toronto), Robert Brandenberger (McGill), René e Hlozek (Toronto/Dunlap), Eve Lee (McGill), Christopher D. Matzner (Toronto), Peter G. Martin (CITA), Ue-Li Pen (CITA), Alison Sills (McMaster), Neil Turok (Perimeter), Larry Widrow (Queen's)

Theoretical Astrophysics in Canada

October 11, 2019

AUTHORS: James E. Taylor (Waterloo), J. Richard Bond (CITA), Jo Bovy (Toronto), Robert Brandenberger (McGill), Renée Hložek (Toronto/Dunlap), Eve Lee (McGill), Christopher D. Matzner (Toronto), Peter G. Martin (CITA), Ue-Li Pen (CITA), Alison Sills (McMaster), Neil Turok (Perimeter), Larry Widrow (Queen’s)

Abstract

Theory plays an essential role in astrophysics, both in planning and motivating observations or experiments and in extracting deeper understanding from their findings. As investment in observational infrastructure grows, deliberate (co-)investment in theory should keep pace. Canada has established a particularly strong reputation in theoretical astrophysics, with leadership in many fields, and with institutions and programs of international stature. We propose strategic ways to build on these strengths so that the investments across astronomy recommended in the LRP reach their full potential.

1 Introduction

The white paper on theory for the US Decadal Survey concludes “*The national investment in observational infrastructure is growing without bound, but in sharp contrast, the national investment in theory has remained constant for decades. This situation threatens the health and vitality of our field. The goal of astronomy and astrophysics is not just to catalog the Universe, but to understand how it works. Without broad support of theoretical work, ranging from theoretical predictions that suggest new observations or instruments, to theoretical interpretation and modelling of existing data, astronomy will be reduced to an expensive and aimless cosmic census.*”

It is worth considering whether the same dire threat applies in Canada. The answer is perhaps not, because in response to similar arguments in the early 1980s, peer-reviewed through NSERC, Canada established a national program in theory through the Canadian Institute for Theoretical Astrophysics (CITA). Indeed, the same US white paper remarks that “*CITA has long been regarded as an intellectual jewel of Canada,*” and adds that “*we should take lessons from this successful program from our Northern neighbor.*” The early investment in CITA helped Canada develop a prominent position in theory internationally. Subsequent growth and the emergence of new centres have added to this strength. Our discipline has remained healthy in Canada because we have understood that progress cannot come from experiment in isolation, but requires constant support from, and interaction with, theory. Yet as our Canadian research community seeks significant new funding for an amazing new generation of observational infrastructure, we need to ensure that support for theory keeps pace, in order to reap the full benefits of our investments.

2 Why do theory?

Theory plays two key roles within astronomy and astrophysics. First, it develops the deep understanding and insight needed to design effective observational or experimental tests of nature, and second, it provides the expertise to analyze and interpret the results of these tests. Here, we discuss these roles and the particular need to invest in theory now.

2.1 Planning

Nearly all major observational facilities are developed to test astrophysical theory. Theory provides the essential “science cases” that motivate individual observing proposals and justify and prioritize longer-term investment in infrastructure. Theory can advance our understanding of the Universe even when it is proven wrong; in fact it is the tension between theory and observation that has often led to the most important advances in physics and astronomy. The discrepancy between observed and predicted fluxes of solar neutrinos, for instance, drove the development of a whole field of experimental physics, eventually culminating in a Nobel prize for Canada (as it turned out, the astrophysical models were correct in this case, while particle physics needed to be revised).

Theory is particularly important in addressing the basic mysteries of cosmology: what was the early evolution of the Universe, and what is the nature of Dark Matter and Dark Energy. Given that current observational probes of these questions are sometimes very limited, theory plays a central role in generating new ideas and new tests that extend our current capabilities.

Conversely, in fields where theory is underdeveloped, we often miss out on observational opportunities. Campbell, Walker, & Yang’s pioneering search for extrasolar planets in the 1980’s, while technically brilliant, was not oriented to find hot Jupiters, leaving a historical first discovery to others; as it was, theory and modelling in this field were delayed for a decade until a flood of data forced a renewed focus on the physics of planet formation and planetary migration. Similarly, with more theoretical work the diffuse infrared emission pervading the high latitude sky in the Milky Way could have been predicted, motivating a more advanced experiment than IRAS, and moving the field ahead by many years.

2.2 Interpretation of Observations

Historically, the most significant observational programs have been closely connected to theory. A recent example was the detection of gravitational waves from mergers of compact objects, where significant theoretical work was also needed just to find the signal, by matching theoretical waveform templates for merging black holes to the strain measurements made by LIGO. A lack of theoretical investment in this field still limits our ability to detect signals from a much broader class of events (e.g., those from eccentric mergers) for which we lack waveform templates.

Theory is also essential to inferring deeper physical truths from observations. Observations of the cosmic microwave background (CMB) provide an excellent example. In this case, the raw observations themselves, essentially just a map of temperature and polarization fluctuations across the sky, are relatively uninteresting. Yet the multi-decade long theoretical effort to understand these data have fuelled much of the recent progress in the field of cosmology, leading to central elements of the current cosmological model such as the Big Bang, cosmic nucleosynthesis, and the Lambda-CDM paradigm.

Finally, in some cases theory helps translate discoveries about particular objects or systems into fundamental discoveries about physics. In the case of the Event Horizon Telescope (EHT), it is only through extensive modelling and simulation that anecdotal information about a single black hole reveals fundamental insights into strong gravity.

2.3 The Need for Theory Now

Although theory is usually invoked to justify observations, direct support for theoretical work is often minimal compared to the resources invested in observations and observational facilities. As theoretical predictions become increasingly complex and time-consuming, requiring months or years of computer time, the incentive to make them in support of observational programs diminishes, and the programs themselves become less well motivated.

As we invest in powerful new facilities, we also need to keep our national theory program healthy and vibrant, to undertake the theoretical research necessary to guide our investments and extract the most scientific return from them. Just as observational capabilities are increasing dramatically, theoretical research has become increasingly complex and demanding. Theoretical work is now often heavily computational, and is beginning to strain the resources of individual research grants, departments, and universities. The need for larger-scale, systematic, organized theory will accelerate in the coming decades with the explosion of unprecedentedly large data sets that will require careful work to extract deeper meaning.

While several prominent fields (e.g., the CMB and several other areas of observational cosmology) have the beginnings of these structures in place, most areas have not received as much theoretical attention. If dedicated support for theoretical analysis were more widely available, major advances could be achieved even with the data that we have already obtained.

Canada has a justified international reputation for expertise in many areas of theoretical astrophysics, and for our national programs. For the Canadian community, ongoing support for theory leverages our contributions to international collaborations. Established experts can play a role in large collaborations that outstrips our direct financial or material contributions; the participation of Canadian experts in high-profile CMB missions provides an excellent example. To provide scientific leadership, we need to produce deep understanding. Rather than supporting large numbers of theorists to simply “match” the data from upcoming observational facilities after it is taken, we need focused effort, active discussion, and the highly developed expertise of individual experts.

With a strong basis in theory, astrophysics is elevated from a mere backdrop for technological research and development to a genuine search for fundamental truths. This is the spirit that a national program of support for theory needs to embody.

3 Theory in Canada

While there is no official registry of theorists in Canada, the membership of CITA Inc. provides a reasonable indication of the size of the community. The current list includes 70 members, most of whom (59/70) hold their primary appointment in an academic department within universities spread coast to coast. These full-time members represent only a fraction of the community, however; the full community includes dozens of PDFs, generally concentrated in centres such as CITA and Perimeter Institute, and hundreds of graduate students. The theory community also nurtures strong ties with many other fields, notably mathematics, engineering, Earth and space science, and high energy and nuclear physics, but also more recently computing, statistics, data science and machine learning. Theoretical work provides astrophysics with an important connection to these other disciplines, fostering innovation and the development of centres of excellence through interdisciplinary work.

Finally, it is worth noting that diversity and gender balance have been ongoing concerns in theoretical astrophysics, as in all of the physical sciences. Currently 60/70 of the members of CITA Inc. are male. More than half the female members have been hired in the last five years. Increased and continual attention to diversity in student recruitment and post-graduate hiring practices can help the community in moving towards a more representative mix.

3.1 CITA and its National Program

CITA lies at the heart of the theory community in Canada. CITA and the national program in theory were established in the early 1980s, through a peer-reviewed process directed by NSERC. Its primary missions are to foster interaction within the Canadian astrophysics community and to serve as an international centre of excellence for theoretical studies in astrophysics. The local roots and international stature of this national program have resulted in a sense of community ownership and collective pride in its accomplishments. Alumni of CITA’s post-doctoral programs hold distinguished positions across Canada and around the globe.

CITA includes a physical centre in Toronto with seven permanent faculty positions, dozens of postdoctoral fellows (PDFs) and senior research associates (RAs), and graduate and undergraduate students recruited through the University of Toronto (U of T) and other institutions. It also directs a national program including National Post-doctoral Fellowships (held jointly at CITA and sponsoring institutions), support for conferences and workshops, and a vibrant visitor program.

Most of CITA’s grant funding is used to support PDFs and RAs. The emphasis on the training of these dynamic and exceptionally talented researchers in an “Advanced Study Institute” model with a particular Canadian spin to it, is at the heart of CITA’s uniqueness, and has catapulted CITA into the top ranks internationally. It has given CITA the critical mass to respond in a timely and collaborative way (often spawning Canadian networks) to emerging hot fields of research, in a high-level energized environment with a positive friendly spirit (perhaps quintessentially

Canadian). CITA is one of the major nodal points in the world for the flow of superb post-PhD researchers who carry so much of the research effort in the field of theoretical astrophysics, and who define the future of our subject as they take their place in permanent academic or research positions. As it is located within Canada's largest university, this post-PhD program is also complemented by rigorous student training through theoretical projects at the undergraduate and graduate levels too.

By continuing to train highly qualified personnel to the highest international standards, CITA is contributing richly to the next generation of theorists. The quality of CITA's training program is clearly measured in the long-term success of its graduates. Alumni of CITA's post-doctoral programs hold distinguished positions across Canada and around the globe. CITA's alumni are having a prodigious impact on the advancement of new knowledge in the field of theoretical astrophysics and other related fields.

A number of other programs also have close connections to CITA. The CIFAR Cosmology and Gravity program, in the first tranche of CIFAR programs, was strongly theoretically oriented (with the participation of theorists Unruh and Israel) and had a strong synergy with CITA (with the participation of Tremaine, Bond, Kaiser, Kofman, and Pen). CIFAR was originally imagined as privately funded and is now a private-public partnership. The astronomy program has evolved to address the theme of the Extreme Universe and is not specially focused on theory.

The GoFAR Canada Excellence Research Chair was selected as one of only 11 awarded in the most recent competition. The award acknowledges the critical role that theory plays in making fundamental breakthroughs relating to gravity, dark matter, and dark energy. This appointment will be based at U of T in CITA, with strong ties to Perimeter. Like the original CIFAR program, the focus of GoFAR is highly theoretical, exploring fundamental physics in gravity and particle astrophysics, to test new ideas in string theory, inflation, and dark energy, some of the most exciting areas in cosmology.

3.2 New and Emerging Centres

A major development in the Canadian landscape in the last two decades has been the expansion and success of Perimeter Institute, a private-public partnership based in Waterloo that spans a broad range of research across theoretical physics. Cosmology has become a central part of Perimeter's focus, with half a dozen full-time faculty and an equal number shared with local universities. In 2017, Perimeter launched its new Centre for the Universe, supporting named postdoctoral fellowships and chairs as well as distinguished visiting research chairs. A new partnership titled "Fundamental Physics with Radio Astronomy" recently launched with DRAO. Other research areas at Perimeter (e.g., particle physics, strong gravity, quantum gravity, and string theory) have significant overlap with cosmology. Perimeter has close ties through cross-appointments and affiliations with other institutions including CITA, U of T, the Universities of Waterloo, McMaster, Guelph and York, and supports large national and international visitor programs.

New institutes have also emerged at a number of universities and departments, reflecting the growing strength of astronomy nationally. While these do not have a specific theory focus, they often include a significant theory component, and provide an important base for Canadian PDFs. They include the MacDonald Institute at Queen's, focusing on astroparticle physics, the McGill Space Institute, focusing on astrophysics, planetary science, and astrobiology, and the Waterloo Centre for Astronomy, focusing on extragalactic survey science, cosmology and compact objects. Similarly, the Dunlap Institute at U of T has a focus on instrumentation. The two national facilities in astrophysics, NRC Herzberg and the Canadian Space Agency (CSA), have been encouraged to support theoretical activities, as in other countries, but do not do so currently.

4 Priorities for Theoretical Astrophysics in Canada

Theory has many priorities in common with all of astrophysics, notably the need for strong national grant funding to individual researchers. Here we focus on the priorities more specific to theory, which are generally in the categories of human resources, digital infrastructure, and communication or outreach – basically facilitating training, communication, interaction and collaboration, both nationally and internationally.

4.1 Highly Qualified Personnel (HQP)

4.1.1 PDFs

Postdoctoral fellows now play an essential role in research. They represent a sweet spot in the balance between expertise and experience on the one hand, and time, enthusiasm and energy on the other. CITA has benefited tremendously from its working model of a large group of postdocs interacting freely with one another and with a smaller number of permanent faculty. Similarly, PDFs play a central role in the more recent programs at Perimeter, Waterloo, McGill, Queen's, Dunlap, and elsewhere. Beyond raw research productivity, PDFs are more open to developments outside their field or institution; thus they serve as drivers of innovation, links across disciplines, and links to the international community. PDF positions provide an essential part of the career path for Canadian post-graduates, and are particularly important in promoting diversity and inclusion.

As it stands, Canada suffers from a shortage of national, merit-based post-doctoral fellowships. While CITA and Perimeter fellowships are primarily merit based, the only other comparable mechanisms are NSERC PDFs, and occasionally Banting fellowships. NSERC PDFs are restricted to Canadian citizens, while Canada has no equivalent of the prestigious US national fellowship programs in astronomy (Hubble, Einstein, etc.). This presents a challenge not only for theory, but across all of astronomy and astrophysics. A fellowship program similar to the US Hubble program was recommended in the previous LRP; an alternative solution might be for CSA to contribute financially to the Hubble program, allowing Hubble-like fellowships to be taken to Canada.

A general question in expanding theory PDF support is whether to tie positions to particular facilities and large projects (such as Euclid, JWST, SKA, and TMT), or to leave them free. The US Theory white paper has recommended some level of co-investment: *“With increasingly long lead times for next generation programs, it is important that the community explicitly adopt a program of co-investment in theory alongside observational missions. The level of this co-investment may vary depending on the nature and scale of the program, but obviously a default of 0% would be unhealthy and exposes the national facilities to tremendous risk – both in underutilized scientific potential as well as community atrophy and apathy over the long periods required to make the discovery machines of the future.”* Similar efforts are proposed in relation to the Canadian LSST Advanced Science Platform (CLASP, PI Hložek) proposal, which would balance the infrastructure support of the CFI grant with funding to support scientific analysis exploiting LSST data.

On the other hand, theory needs to be fostered not just within but also outside of specific observational infrastructure. Inspiration through the latter can lead to future facilities that would not otherwise be contemplated. An excellent example in Canada is the CHIME project, which developed a radically new approach to radio observations that had not been anticipated in prior long-term planning. The current practice at CITA and PI is that fellowships are open to all theorists, regardless of whether their research relates to a specific observational initiative or not. We recommend that this balance be retained, and that any future co-investment not undermine the base of independent positions available.

4.1.2 Students and HQP Training

Student engagement and training also form a crucial part of the theory community's activity. Student engagement is important to guarantee succession and a steady stream of HQP in the field; it also helps address pressing long-term problems of diversity, and provides value to society outside the field. Finally, student engagement leverages research grant funding, generating a much wider impact for NSERC investment in the field, as students contribute to research through their work.

Internships are an effective means of undergraduate engagement, and can help direct talented students to graduate work in theory. Currently CITA, though not the CITA grant, supports undergraduates through summer programs and scholarships, including the NSERC USRA program that supports summer students nationally. Summer schools and 'bootcamps' in technical fields such as high-performance computing, run through CITA, Compute Canada, and/or local high-performance computing (HPC) networks, also provide an important means of engagement, recruitment, and training. The social aspect of these activities is essential – summer students and workshop participants benefit tremendously from exposure to a professional research environment, interacting with postdocs

and faculty and getting to know the theory community. While workshops can be organized ad-hoc and focused on specific topics, having established, long-term summer programs with a more general focus generates international visibility and a predictable recruitment stream.

At the graduate level, work in theory often requires a significant formal background that might not be part of regular undergraduate curricula. In fields such as hydrodynamics, radiative transfer, strong gravity, or advanced statistical techniques, dedicated workshops and summer schools are essential to provide training to bridge this gap. Formal degree programs such as the PSI Masters program at Perimeter, now one of the most prominent programs globally, provide broad training with an opening into all areas of theoretical physics and related disciplines, and have benefited recruitment in astrophysics in particular.

One challenge not often recognized is the logistical burden of providing specialized graduate training in theory in smaller university departments. Currently, only a handful of Canadian institutions can offer a large set of regular graduate courses in astrophysics, whereas a much larger number train graduate students in the field. One possible solution is to move some graduate training to the digital domain, following the example of massive open on-line courses (MOOCs). While the technology to do this is largely mature, funding, organization, and governance remain challenges. As it stands, visitor programs and digital presentation archives provide some useful tools for graduate students across Canada to learn about activity in the large centres.

Overall, in terms of funding, we recommend support for a portfolio of training opportunities and resources, including individual internships and scholarships, local workshops and bootcamps, but also higher-profile recurring summer schools with a more general focus. Graduate training should also be promoted and disseminated digitally, to make it more cost-effective and more widely available.

4.2 Cohesion and Rejuvenation in the Theory Community

Dedicated meetings are particularly important to the theory community. Whereas observational projects often require consensus, compromise, and long-term planning, theory usually evolves on a shorter timescale, involves more individual work, and consequently benefits from a greater degree of argument, confrontation, and challenge. In the words of the US white paper, “*Unlike engineering, where there are multiple solutions, [...] theoretical work is either correct or incorrect. It is thus critical that theorists have a forum for vigorous argument.*” Meetings such as the CASCA AGM do not always provide the best forum for theory, as the talk format is more suited to the presentation of results, rather than discussion or argument about them.

Theory-specific meetings are currently organized by a large number of departments and institutions nationally, and are subsidized through CITA’s support program. These help to knit together the Canadian astrophysics community and improve its international visibility. To maintain a healthy community, we recommend continued support for meetings at different levels, including

- Larger, recurring conference series with a more general focus, such as the Kingston Meetings, which help build up community and generate international visibility.
- Smaller workshops with a narrower focus, to respond to short-term, important observational or theoretical advances or results; historically, CITA, PI, and CIFAR have supported and sometimes organized these.
- “Challenges” or workshops to develop theory or analysis tools in a particular area, or to confront techniques; examples include code comparison projects (the pioneering Santa Barbara cluster focus and descendants), the STEP meetings in weak lensing, and other collective attempts to advance methods in a field.
- Large or small meetings focused on students, as discussed in the previous section.

Given that current and future students are now “digital natives”, having been exposed to social media platforms continuously since childhood, they may be receptive to a wider range of non-traditional meeting formats, such as virtual meeting sessions on-line, the increasingly ubiquitous “hackathons”, or others. As discussed in the Low-carbon future LRP white paper, increased digital connection and participation has several other important benefits and should be a goal in future conference or workshop planning.

While meetings are the most visible forum for interaction, discussion, and community-building, research networks and visitor programs, whether for faculty or for students, provide important individual connections. Continued support for visitor programs and student scholarships/internships is a priority for theory in Canada. CITA Council also provides a potential platform for fostering national research connections, and could be expanded and re-organized to include former CITA alumni and/or international collaborators, and to hold regular, independent meetings.

4.3 International Engagement

Theory plays an important part in leveraging Canada’s contributions to large international projects; by supplying experts and authorities, we can often “punch above our weight” in these joint ventures. Maintaining, developing and promoting Canada’s theoretical expertise makes sense as part of our overall investment in astrophysics.

Beyond support for theory within Canada, to promote our international visibility and connections we recommend

- Support for Canadian theorists to attend international meetings and/or visit and collaborate abroad.
- Support for theory meetings in Canada with international visibility, such as the Kingston meetings, as discussed in the previous section.
- Support for international visiting students, PDFs, and researchers, through HQP exchange programs.

CITA has piloted PDF exchange programs with ASIAA, CCA, KITP, and MPA, with exchange visits lasting from one week to two months. It is also developing international partnerships with a number of institutions, e.g., KITP, Carnegie, MPIA, and KIAA, to enhance its ability in attracting the most outstanding young postdoctoral fellows. Joint fellowships have a multiplicative advantage because they provide a longer fellowship duration at two institutions simultaneously. They allow fellows to maximize their connections and explore a wider range of research possibilities. As a result, they allow a much broader pool of talent to be attracted to Canada.

4.4 Digital Infrastructure

In the domain of digital infrastructure, theorists have many interests and concerns in common with the rest of the field, as discussed in the LRP white papers on computation. Much of theoretical astrophysics relies on access to high-performance computing (HPC) for numerical simulations and model testing, and theorists in general and CITA in particular have been at the forefront of developing infrastructure, both hardware and software. National support for HPC does exist within Canada, through Compute Canada, regional networks, and dedicated resources at CITA. In particular, CITA has historically provided advanced in-house computing at a mid-scale level and shared this across the country. It offers expertise in parallel computing, as well as support by highly-trained professional staff.

Beyond this base, theory could benefit from additional support for the digital products of theoretical research:

- Current simulations have expanded to exceptional scales, representing millions of hours of CPU time and generating Petabytes of data. The Canadian-led “Tian-Nu” simulation ran on over 13,000 nodes in China, reflecting the unfilled need for capability computing. (The Compute Canada model of a uniform share of resources allocated over the year is also poorly matched to leading HPC initiatives, which require concentrated resources for short sprints, and so additional capacity would help there too.) Archiving the results of numerical simulations and making them accessible to a broader community is essential to make effective use of the investment of time and effort required to generate them. The Canadian Astronomical Data Centre (CADC) provides one obvious place to develop such capacity.
- Simulation access should not be restricted to passive storage; often subsequent analysis and post-processing require as much or more work than the initial simulations themselves. Thus, access should be through platforms that can support large, remote analysis jobs by external users.

- Similarly, given the ad-hoc nature of code development and maintenance in our field, analysis software related to simulations should be implemented, documented, and maintained through the same sites, just as observatories often develop and host data reduction software.

In common with the rest of astrophysics, supporting this model of archiving and access would have implications for infrastructure, staffing, planning, and management. Support for such projects could come from the usual channels, but also through the broader-based funding available for digital infrastructure (e.g., Compute Canada, CANARIE, etc.).

4.5 Dissemination and Outreach

As a discipline, astrophysics benefits from tremendous media exposure and the resulting public interest and support. However, images of newly-discovered objects dominate reporting of the field – theory is harder to present, explain, and motivate. To understand that the discipline consists of more than just ‘looking through a telescope’, theoretical results should be presented and promoted at a national level, in ways that allow easy media engagement.

Major results, such as the EHT images, speak for themselves and are heavily promoted by the individual institutions involved, but as a field we could promote a broader range of material through a national showcase on the CASCA website. Providing a landing spot there for media to make contact with researchers, access the CASCA press officer, and quickly find relevant links to high quality material would help foster public appreciation and support for the theoretical work that underpins the observational results.

A related idea is to maintain a national inventory of recorded talks, with links to the speakers. Here too, talk archives are available within some institutions (e.g., CITA and PI) but could be extended and enhanced via a national page, administered by the CADC and/or CASCA, that provided indexing and/or links to these archives. Just as professional astronomers benefit from having a single source for preprints through arXiv, our students and the public would benefit from having a single portal for science results, while links back to the hosting institutions would guarantee that the credit and visibility are correctly assigned to them. Perimeter already hosts PIRSA, a large repository of public lectures, seminars, and lecture courses, and is contemplating a major expansion.

Finally, dedicated national prizes in theory, particularly at junior (graduate thesis) levels, would encourage and recognize the next generation of researchers. These could be tied in to the CASCA website, providing ready material for a spotlight page there.

5 Conclusions

Theory plays essential roles in strategic planning for future observations and facilities, and in extracting value and meaning from the data they obtain. Without theory, astronomers would not know what questions to ask, which questions they can hope to answer now and in the future, or what the answers mean at a deeper level. Strong support for theory is essential to keep astrophysics vibrant, balanced, and cost-effective.

To support and develop Canada’s theory community, we recommend:

- Expanding national PDF opportunities in theoretical astrophysics, via the CITA National Fellow program, CSA funding for a Hubble matching program, PDFs linked to large observational facilities, and other mechanisms.
- Providing more training opportunities at undergraduate, graduate, and postdoctoral levels, including short meetings or workshops with a narrower focus, recurring summer schools with a broader focus, and digital courses for graduate students.
- Supporting meetings focused on theory, including recurring meetings with international visibility (such as the Kingston meetings).

- Developing joint, collaborative digital facilities not simply for running simulations, but also for hosting the resulting data and supporting subsequent analysis. These facilities could also host and maintain analysis software, and provide dedicated technical support.
- Recognizing and publicizing theory results along with observational ones, through dedicated theory prizes, dedicated space on the CASCA website, and a centralized landing place for media.

Each of these initiatives would build on Canada's prestigious national program in theory, and leverage Canada's contribution to astrophysics globally.

Acknowledgements: The authors acknowledge extensive discussions with and input from Juna Kollmeier and the authors of the US Decadal Survey white paper on theory, as well as the authors of the LRP white papers on a Low-carbon future and on LSST.

6 Addressing the LRP Criteria

1: How does the proposed initiative result in fundamental or transformational advances in our understanding of the Universe?

Theory provides the framework for addressing the big mysteries of the Universe, such as its origin and the nature of Dark Matter and Dark Energy. It provides essential insight and expertise to interpret complex data and design the next generation of experiments. Most prominent science projects in astrophysics would be inconceivable without strong, dedicated theoretical support.

2: What are the main scientific risks and how will they be mitigated?

The main risk is that support for theory, and Canada's reputation in this area, will fade away under the pressure of short-term demands related to the delivery of new observational infrastructure.

3: Is there the expectation of and capacity for Canadian scientific, technical or strategic leadership?

Yes – internationally, Canada's national theory program is held up as an example to emulate.

4: Is there support from, involvement from, and coordination within the relevant Canadian community and more broadly?

Yes, historically and ongoing through CITA Inc., and bolstered by new networks and centres.

5: Will this program position Canadian astronomy for future opportunities and returns in 2020-2030 or beyond 2030?

Yes. Investment in theory will help ensure that we get the most out of our current and planned infrastructure, and will help argue the case for further development of the field.

6: In what ways is the cost-benefit ratio, including existing investments and future operating costs, favourable?

Support for theory is comparatively cheap. In principle, we could leave major investment in observational infrastructure to the rest of the world and still maintain a strong reputation internationally by just doing theory. Theory can help identify strategic observational and experimental priorities, and theoretical expertise allows us to “punch above our weight” in international collaborations.

7: What are the main programmatic risks and how will they be mitigated?

Theoretical advances are not simply locked to the schedules of large facilities, and so benefits accrue even when observational projects get delayed. On the other hand, the timeline for theoretical progress in any one area is less predictable than for an engineering project. Support for a broad base of endeavours is key to maintaining overall research momentum and impact.

8: Does the proposed initiative offer specific tangible benefits to Canadians, including but not limited to interdisciplinary research, industry opportunities, HQP training, EDI, outreach or education?

Theory provides a steady source of HQP trained in physics, mathematics, computing, and advanced statistical techniques. Theoretical training often overlaps significantly with the needs of other disciplines, and individuals moving out of the field routinely take leadership positions in big data, finance, global risk management, and many other analytical and quantitative areas that have tangible benefits to Canadian society.